

Chemical composition analysis of germanate glass by alkalimetric titration of germanate mannitol complex

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Abstract : A titrimetric method has been developed for the determination of germanium in glass. Germanium anion in aqueous solution combine with two molecules of mannitol to form a germanate mannitol complex in presence of sufficient mannitol. The complex is moderately strong acid and germanium can be determined by alkalimetric titration. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective and the method is successfully applied for the determination of germanium in glass.

Keywords : Germanate glass, mannitol complex, germanium, alkalimetric titration.

Germanium containing glasses¹ have become important materials in the telecommunications and optical industries. Therefore, an exactly known glass composition is often necessary. When preparing glasses by melting their starting materials, the liquid vapourises to a considerable extent. Since chemical composition of the vapour species is in general, different from that of the melt, the melt composition changes. It is therefore desirable to analyse the resulting glass composition. Among the available methods germanium has been determined gravimetrically^{2,3} after precipitating it as tripyrocatechol germanate. Titrimetric determination of germanium is based on the formation of tripyrocatechol germanic acid^{4,5}. Germanium is determined by indirect complexometric titration with EDTA⁶. Most of these methods are lengthy and causes error. Germanium hydroxide combine in aqueous solution with mannitol, HOCH₂[CH(OH)]₄CH₂OH to form a germanate-mannitol complex⁷. This complex is a moderately strong mono basic acid and germanium can be determined by alkalimetric titration. The end point of the titration is determined visually in presence of a suitable indicator. The present work utilizes this reaction for the determination of germanium in glass. The error has been eliminated by standardizing the alkali solution against a solution of known amount of germanium. In this study, a simple and rapid procedure for the dissolution of germanate glass has been fine tuned which involves dissolution of the sample in alkali solution using polyethylene vessel as the reaction chamber. The proposed method was applied to NBS SRM germanate glasses to assess the accuracy

and precision of the concentration of germanium measured by this procedure. The method has been successfully applied to the determination of germanium in germanium dioxide, germanate glass and germanosilicate materials.

Results and discussion

Direct titration of germanic acid with alkali is not possible since germanic acid is only weakly dissociated in aqueous solution and it is very difficult to find an indicator which gives a sharp color change. However, germanium hydroxide combine in aqueous solution with polyhydric alcohol like mannitol in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 to form a germanate mannitol complex⁷. Germanium hydroxide in alkaline solution has been considered⁸ to dissociate in the way :

If germanium hydroxide dissociates in the above manner it would be difficult to form germanate mannitol complex. It is known, however, that germanium combines with halogen element¹⁰, X, to form GeX₅⁻ or GeX₆²⁻. Thus germanium hydroxide has been considered¹¹ to dissociate as :

When mannitol is added to germanium hydroxide solution germanium ion combines with two molecules of mannitol to form germanate mannitol complex. Formation constant of germanium mannitol complex⁸ is $-\log K_a = 9.02$. A relatively great increase in the solution acidity

during the reaction between weak germanic acid and mannitol makes it possible to easily determine germanium by alkalimetric titration with a suitable indicator.

The principle of the alkalimetric determination of germanic acid is as follows : in the beginning of analysis the excess acidity of the solution is neutralized to a degree which leaves germanic acid in free state using indicators such as methyl orange (pH 3.0–4.4), methyl red (pH 4.2–6.2) etc. After addition of mannitol, the complex acid formed is titrated using a second indicator such as phenolphthalein (pH ~9.0).

During acid digestion of the alkaline extract, color of methyl orange or methyl red indicator disappears. Fresh addition of the indicator is required until color of the indicator persists. It causes consumption of some alkali during the first end point titration (neutralization).

In order to find out a suitable indicator for neutralization of free acid as well as for the final titration of mannitogermanic acid, *p*-nitrophenol (pH 5.0–7.0) and bromothymol blue indicators (pH 6.0–7.6) have been chosen. Bromothymol blue was found to serve both the purposes. The end point indicating a change from pale yellow to greenish blue at pH 6.5 was sharp and sensitive. Moreover, at pH 6.5 the precipitation of hydroxides of other cations present in glass is less.

The effect of mannitol concentration on the alkalimetric titration of mannitogermanic acid complex at pH 6.5 was studied. A series of 50 ml solution containing 40 mg of germanium was taken at pH 6.5 and complexed with mannitol (addition 5 g to 25 g of mannitol) followed by the neutralization of mannitogermanic acid with standard NaOH. Fig. 1 shows that below 14 g of mannitol/50 ml of solution low results were obtained due to partial for-

Fig. 1. Effect of mannitol concentration on the complete formation of mannitogermanic acid.

mation of mannitogermanic acid complex. Addition of mannitol at least 15 g/50 ml of solution containing 40 mg of germanium is essential for complete formation of the acid complex.

Boron undergoes similar reaction with mannitol and thus interferes seriously with this method. The interfering effect due to boron has been successfully overcome by volatilisation of boron as methyl borate.

A study on the effect of fluorine upto 50 mg shows that upto 20 mg of fluorine in 50 ml solution containing 40 mg of germanium, there is no significant effect on the determination of germanium (Fig. 2). However, with greater amounts of fluorine, higher germanium results are obtained.

Fig. 2. Effect of fluorine concentration on the alkalimetric titration of mannitogermanic acid.

Germanium content of a series of germanium hydroxide solution were determined by following the present procedure and the results are shown in Table 1.

The present method was validated by the determination of germanium in NBS standard reference germanate glasses and the results are shown in Table 2. The results were found to be agreed well with the certified values. The method is rapid and accurate and has been successfully applied to the determination of germanium in germanium bearing materials (Table 2).

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents were used unless otherwise stated. Distilled water was made free from CO₂ by bubbling with nitrogen gas.

Standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.1 N) : Sodium hydroxide solution free from carbon dioxide was pre-

Table 1. Determination of germanium

Ge taken (mg)	Ge found ^a (mg)	Relative error (%)	Standard deviation (mg)	RSD (%)	Students' 't' value ^b
40.00	40.02	+0.05	0.03	0.07	1.49
32.00	32.01	+0.03	0.02	0.06	1.12
24.00	23.98	-0.08	0.05	0.21	0.90
16.00	16.03	+0.18	0.06	0.37	1.12
8.00	7.98	-0.25	0.07	0.88	0.64

^aMean of five determinations.^bStudents' 't' test for 5% level of significance = 2.78.

Table 2. Analysis of germanium bearing materials

Materials	Certified value concentration, %	Observed value ^a concentration, %	RSD (%)	Recovery (%)
Germanate glass				
NBS SRM 1872 (K-453)	28.43	28.41 ± 0.04	0.14	99.93
Germanate glass				
NBS SRM 1872 (K-491)	26.10	26.12 ± 0.06	0.23	100.08
Germanate glass				
NBS SRM 1872 (K-968)	25.93	25.90 ± 0.03	0.12	99.88
Germanium silicate	36.40 ^b	36.47 ± 0.10	0.27	100.19
Germanium oxide	98.60 ^b	98.63 ± 0.13	0.13	100.03

^aMean of five determinations.^bValue obtained by standard method⁵.

pared by a standard method¹¹. This solution was stored in a polyethylene container, delivered into the burette with a siphon using pressure from a nitrogen gas reservoir and used as the titrant without exposure to carbon dioxide of the air.

Standard germanium solution was prepared by dissolving high purity germanium dioxide (99.99%) in 20% sodium hydroxide solution and dilute to 250 ml in a calibrated flask (1 ml = 4.00 mg Ge).

D-Mannitol : The reagent was purified by recrystallisation from the ethanol-water solution (1 : 1 ethanol to water by volume). After recrystallisation, no acidic impurities could be detected.

Bromothymol blue indicator : 0.5% solution in alcohol.

Procedure : About 0.1 g of powdered and dried (105 ± 5 °C) sample was taken in a 250 ml polyethylene beaker. Sample was moistened with few drops of water and 10 ml of 20% sodium hydroxide solution was added. The mixture was kept on a water bath for 15–20 min to

make a clear solution. The solution was diluted to 50 ml and neutralised by dropwise addition of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide in presence of bromothymol blue indicator to the bluish green end point (pH 6.5). About 15 g of mannitol was added to the solution and the released mannitogermanic acid was titrated with standard NaOH solution to the same bluish green end point. A reagent blank was carried out and necessary correction was made.

The percentage of germanium is then given by $(100 A \times B)/W$. Where A is the ml of standard sodium hydroxide solution required to titrate mannitogermanic acid complex. B is the germanium equivalent to 1 ml of standard sodium hydroxide and W is the weight of the sample present in the aliquot or in the total solution.

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